

Image Generation combined with Super-Resolution: A Medical Image Pipeline

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Abstract

Cancer remains a leading cause of mortality worldwide, with breast and lung cancers accounting for many cases. Accurate and early diagnosis relies on high-quality medical imaging, yet data scarcity and limited resolution constrain robust computational tools. This work presents a pipeline integrating synthetic image generation with super-resolution to improve the quality and availability of medical imaging. Our approach splits the problem into two: anatomical coherence and variability are handled by 3D generative adversarial networks (GANs), while fine structural detail is enhanced via Real-ESRGAN. The framework was evaluated on breast MRI and lung CT datasets. Despite some limitations, results demonstrate that combining generative modelling with super-resolution can expand medical imaging datasets and improve fidelity, contributing to more precise and reliable cancer diagnosis, as confirmed by quantitative metrics, perceptual evaluation, and expert feedback.

Keywords: Breast Cancer; Deep Learning; Image Super-Resolution; Lung Cancer; Medical Image Analysis; Synthetic Image Generation

1 Introduction

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide, with breast and lung cancers representing the most prevalent forms across populations. Early and accurate diagnosis remains critical for improving survival rates, and medical imaging modalities such as computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are essential in guiding clinical decisions. However, the effectiveness of imaging-driven diagnosis is often limited by the availability of high-quality annotated data and the intrinsic resolution constraints of different imaging modalities.

Recent advances in generative artificial intelligence (AI) have shown promise in mitigating these challenges. Generative models such as GANs and diffusion models can synthesize anatomically coherent images, providing a means to augment existing datasets. In parallel, deep learning-based image super-resolution (ISR or SR) methods have emerged as powerful tools for enhancing the quality and level of detail of images, going beyond traditional interpolation-based techniques. Together, these approaches open new possibilities for improving both the quantity and quality of medical image data available for analysis.

In this work, we propose a pipeline that combines synthetic image generation with super-resolution to address these limitations. By decoupling the tasks of structural variability and fine-detail reconstruction, we aim to generate anatomically realistic yet high-quality medical images. We validate this approach in two clinically significant use cases - breast MRI and lung CT - demonstrating its potential to enhance data availability and support more reliable diagnostic workflows.

Unlike previous studies that mainly focus on synthetic data generation or super-resolution independently, our work places greater emphasis on evaluating their combined impact within practical clinical use cases. In addition to standard quantitative metrics, we incorporate a Visual Turing Test with expert radiologists to directly assess perceptual realism, bridging the gap between algorithmic performance and clinical applicability. This dual perspective highlights not only the pipeline's technical feasibility but also its potential to meaningfully support diagnostic practice. The

code related to this work is publicly available in a GitHub repository¹.

2 Methodology

2.1 Datasets

We evaluated the proposed pipeline on two cancer imaging contexts: breast MRI and lung CT. All datasets were preprocessed in the same manner, which consisted of min-max normalisation and Hounsfield unit adjustment. Moreover, all samples / slices were resized from 512^3 to 64^3 and 128^3 in order to ease the generative process and make the task of super-resolution feasible. Each use case relied on two separate data collections: the public *Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI* [5] and a private aggregation of 89 volumes in partnership with the *Champalimaud Foundation* made up the totality of breast MRI data ; the *LIDC-IDRI* [1] and *RIDER* [2] datasets comprised all lung CT scans used in this project.

2.2 Experimental Protocol

All optimised models were chosen to be GANs for the purposes of computational efficiency and training flexibility. The architectures chosen for both tasks were:

- The 3D Wasserstein GAN (**3D WGAN**) [4] which promotes training stability and a more reliable convergence by using the Wasserstein distance and a critic model rather than a discriminator ;
- The 3D α -Wasserstein GAN with Gradient Penalty (**3D α -WGAN-GP**) [3] which expands upon the previous work through the replacement of weight clipping for a penalty with the aim of increasing convergence speed and stabilising gradients ;
- The 3D Hierarchical Amortised GAN (**3D HA-GAN**) [7], a work focused on solving memory limitations by introducing a multiple resolution hierarchical framework and amortised inference ;
- The Real Enhanced Super-Resolution GAN (**Real-ESRGAN**) [8], a model that extends previous works on super-resolution GANs through the use of a discriminator module with perceptual losses ;

As it pertains to the experiments performed, it should firstly be said that the application of generative models resulted in 64^3 and 128^3 samples, although HA-GAN only handled the latter. Breast MRI data was kept as a control group for evaluating adversarial performance, while lung CT data was tested under two different training regimes: the first experiment included a generator-discriminator update per iteration ratio of 1-to-1 and the second a ratio of 5-to-1. This allowed us to measure the discriminator's sensitivity to overfitting or mode collapse.

All super-resolution experiments were trained to perform $4\times$ enhancement. Experiments were performed using each imaging modality separately and also a combination of the two. The latter was then tested on each imaging technique dataset so as to assess the Real-ESRGAN's ability to generalise between different modalities. Final experiments also included fine-tuning and the introduction of heavy blurring to the real low-resolution (LR) samples, with bicubic interpolation serving as the baseline comparison. Further experimental details are also included in [6].

¹https://github.com/brightside51/IbPRIA2025_Medical_GenSR_Pipeline

2.3 Performance Evaluation

Model performance was measured using both pixel-level and perceptual metrics, including Structural Similarity (SSIM), Multi-Scale Structural Similarity (MS-SSIM), Fréchet Inception Distance (FID), Inception Score (IS), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD). Finally, resulting samples also underwent a Visual Turing Test (VTT) with two board-certified radiologists, who were given the task of discriminating between synthetic and real samples.

3 Results & Discussion

Figure 1: Qualitative results comprised of a middle and peripheral slice of synthetic 3D breast MRI volumes created by all 3 proposed models for both 64^3 and 128^3 size experiments. Rather than 64^3 -sized scans created by HA-GAN (which were not tested), the **bottom left corner** includes middle slices of two real data samples (with sizes 64^3 on the left and 128^3 on the right) for comparison.

Among the generative models, HA-GAN was the one to perform the best when trained with breast MRI data, particularly at higher resolutions, even despite having been trained for less iterations, which leads us to believe in the efficiency of adding local high-resolution (HR) patches. On the other hand, for lower resolutions, WGAN struggles with artifacts and deformities, whereas α -WGAN seems to leverage its use of latent space modelling to reduce blurriness and the possibility of mode collapse, thus achieving better results. Qualitative results can be found in figure 1.

Figure 2: Qualitative results comprised of slices of synthetic 3D lung CT volumes created by all 3 proposed models for both 64^3 and 128^3 size experiments and for each of the two experiments performed. Rather than 64^3 -sized scans created by HA-GAN (which were not tested), the **bottom left corner** includes a middle slices of two real data samples (with sizes 64^3 on the left and 128^3 on the right) for comparison. On the right, slices of unrealistic and faulty samples created by each model may also be found.

For the lower resolution of 64^3 , WGAN and α -WGAN experiments often displayed reduced variability, being able to clearly outline major structures but not minor airways and pulmonary vessels for example. As such, quality differences between the two mostly revolve around saturation and texture calibre. Non-displayed qualitative metrics also seem to indicate that WGAN suffers from mode collapse, seeing as artificial samples were very much alike after a certain number of iterations. Higher resolution samples display a noticeable increase in quality and detail, as well as some more artifacts. Once again, HA-GAN is the one to perform the best for both major and minor details. Of the two experiments, the second seems to produce the best results, indicating that the generator does indeed need to be updated more often to push the discriminator further.

Figure 3: Qualitative results comprised of slices from real and Real-ESRGAN synthetic 3D lung CT and breast MRI volumes with a size of 512×512 after 4x augmentation from 128×128 . The comparison can be made between the ground truth (which the exception with synthetic data for which we have none), what is achieved using this model, and the traditional method of bicubic interpolation.

Despite quantitative metric incoherences, the Real-ESRGAN architecture demonstrated significant perceptual improvements over bicubic interpolation, especially when trained on both modalities. Furthermore, cross-modality training further improved generalization across imaging types. VTT results and the radiologists' accuracy (71.7% for breast MRI and 67% for lung CT data) indicate difficulty in distinguishing synthetic from real samples. Despite resolutions being below the clinical standard, their feedback also pointed out excessive symmetry and unnatural textures as clear-cut signs.

4 Conclusions

This work introduced a pipeline that combines generative adversarial networks with super-resolution techniques to expand and enhance medical imaging datasets. Applied to breast MRI and lung CT data, the framework demonstrated the capacity to generate anatomically plausible synthetic volumes and improve structural detail through 4x resolution enhancement. Despite these promising outcomes, generating high-resolution images remains challenging, with artifacts and loss of fine structures still present. Future work will explore diffusion-based generative models and improved training strategies to achieve higher fidelity and variability.

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References

- [1] Samuel G. Armato III et al. [Data From LIDC-IDRI](#), 2015.
- [2] Samuel G. Armato III et al. [The reference image database to evaluate response to therapy in lung cancer \(RIDER\) project: a resource for the development of change-analysis software](#). *Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 2008.
- [3] Ishaan Gulrajani et al. [Improved training of wasserstein GANs](#). 2017.
- [4] Gihyun Kwon et al. [Generation of 3D brain MRI using auto-encoding generative adversarial networks](#). 2019.
- [5] Ashirbani Saha et al. [A machine learning approach to radiogenomics of breast cancer: a study of 922 subjects and 529 DCE-MRI features](#). *British Journal of Cancer*, 2018.
- [6] Pedro Sousa et al. [Enhancing medical image analysis: a pipeline combining synthetic image generation and super-resolution](#). In *Pattern Recognition and Image Analysis*, 2025.
- [7] Li Sun et al. [Hierarchical amortized GAN for 3D high resolution medical image synthesis](#). *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 2022.
- [8] Xintao Wang et al. [Real-ESRGAN: training real-world blind super-resolution with pure synthetic data](#). 2021.